

FAILURE CRITERIA FOR COMPOSITE ISOGRID STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT: The composite isogrid concept was selected for the payload fairing of the Minotaur launch vehicle. Longitudinal and helical blade stiffeners are bonded to the skin, forming the characteristic isogrid pattern. Compared to sandwich structures, this concept has the advantage of smaller manufacturing costs and lighter weight. To reduce weight the skin pockets are allowed to buckle visibly up to about .5 cm peak displacement.

The failure modes identified for the composite isogrid structure are: (1) maximum strain, (2) global buckling, (3) skin-stiffener joint in tension, (4) skin-stiffener joint in shear, and (5) skin-stiffener joint subject to skin peel-off loads. While the first four criteria are quite straightforward, development of the last criteria required extensive test and analysis effort.

As a result of skin buckling waves, a bending moment develops in the skin-stiffener joint (T-joint). Detailed finite element models of the T-joint were used to identify the critical area of the joint, the fillet radius. A small number of T-joint specimens were tested, and the first strain invariant corresponding to failure was obtained by applying the test loads to the finite element models of the joint.

Three cylindrical test panels were constructed and loaded in longitudinal compression until failure. Finite element models of the panels were created and loaded in similar manner. The internal loads extracted from the models of the test panels were applied to the detailed T-joint model. The first strain invariant was calculated corresponding to different load increments and compared to that of the T-joint specimens at failure. The joint analysis method was calibrated with the test panel results, and an allowable strain criteria based on first strain invariant was selected.

The other failure criteria were also evaluated to determine which one is critical when the test panels failed. Depending on the skin thickness and grid geometry several criteria were elevated at panel failure, but the T-joint failure due to skin bending loads was always dominant. The composite isogrid structure failure criteria were validated by tests and applied to the sizing of the Minotaur payload fairing. The joint failure resulting from skin bending was critical for all test panels and is precipitated by skin buckling. Increasing skin thickness to avoid buckling results in low strains in skin and stiffeners. Using the failure criteria described in this paper, it is possible to improve the joint design and achieve a more efficient use of material properties.

KEYWORDS: grid-stiffened, buckling, failure criteria, testing, composite

INTRODUCTION

Composite isogrid structures consist of stiffeners (or ribs) co-cured on the skin as shown in Figure 1. The skin is allowed to buckle, resulting in localized, non-linear structural behavior. Both the stiffeners and the skin are laid using a tow placing machine, yielding lower manufacturing costs compared with a sandwich design. The resulting fairing design in the current example was also significantly lighter than an existing sandwich design for a Minotaur launch vehicle fairing.

Figure 1. Minotaur Fairing Composite Isogrid Structure

The skin buckling waves tend to peel the skin from the stiffeners. Once a stiffener disbonds, the structural integrity of the structure is compromised. Tests showed the joint is the critical component of this design. A new failure criterion was developed for the stiffener to skin joint and successfully applied to the design of the Minotaur fairing.

FAILURE CRITERIA

Failure criteria for the composite grid-stiffened structure are: (1) max strain, (2) global buckling, (3) joint failure resulting from shear, (4) joint failure resulting from skin pull-off (tension), and (5) joint failure resulting from skin peeling (skin bending). While the first two criteria are common to all composite structures, the last three are specific to the grid-stiffened panels. The loads acting on connecting elements drive the joint failure: F_R the radial pull-off load, F_Z the shear load, and M_Z the bending moment (Figure 2).

Shear Joint Failure. The shear load is transferred to the skin through the adhesive layer. The shear load in the stiffener element is readily available from the results of the finite element analysis and is used to calculate the inter-laminar shear stress.

Figure 2. Joint Loads

Pull-off Joint Failure happens when the tensile strength of the adhesive layer between the stiffener and skin is exceeded. This failure mode could become critical for very thick skins that have high bending stiffness, but is not critical for aerospace structures.

Peel-off joint failure is the critical criteria for most aerospace structures that use thin skins. The bending moment M_Z causes the skin to peel-off from the stiffener. Skin buckling causes a sharp increase of the bending moment. For thin structures skin peel-off occurs after local skin buckling and usually happens before the other criteria become critical. The failure initiates in the fillet radius that is made only from resin (Figure 3). T-specimen tests were used to determine the critical strain in the fillet radius. Both the first strain invariant J_1 and Von Mises strain could be used for this purpose. Using T-specimens to develop an allowable fillet radius strain has the advantage to include the effects of manufacturing imperfections and thermal residual strains similar to the actual part.

Figure 3. Joint First Strain Invariant (J1)

The number of T specimens was not large enough to determine the allowable strain through statistical analysis. A $J1_{allowable} = 0.7 J1_{average}$ was selected after calibration with 3 panel tests and used for sizing the Minotaur fairing. The joint loads from the coarse mesh panel model were applied to a detailed joint model. The J1 obtained from the detailed joint model is compared with the allowable strain to determine the joint margin of safety (Figure 4). $J1_{average}$ was found by applying the average specimen failure load to a fine mesh model and assessing the peak J1 value for that calculation.

Figure 4. Skin Peel-off Failure Criteria

Theoretically the transition between the coarse mesh panel model and fine mesh detail joint model could be done through displacements or loads. However the mesh of the detailed model is orders of magnitude finer than the panel mesh and therefore has a very different stiffness. Enforcing the displacements of the coarse mesh model on the fine mesh joint model would yield unreliable results.

The loads boundary approach on the other hand is less sensitive to the change in stiffness. The joint loads were obtained as free body grid point forces applied to the elements at each side of the joint. The joint loads for each skin element were reduced at a point located at the distance W from the joint and then applied to the detailed joint model (Figure 5). Since in our application the stiffener (rib) was much thicker than the skin, it was practical to constrain the displacements of the stiffener top section rather than

applying boundary loads at that section. This also solved the problem of constraining the free body motion of the detailed joint model.

Figure 5. Application of Boundary Loads to Joint Detailed Model

T-SPECIMEN TESTS

T-specimens were fabricated and tested to determine the strength of the rib/skin joint in a simulated skin-buckling mode. Skin pocket buckling induces a bending load at the rib/skin joint, and the test fixtures were designed to induce similar loading at the joint. Specimens with three different skin thicknesses were tested: 3-ply, 6-ply and 8-ply skins. The 8-ply skin specimens were tested first and used an earlier test fixture, shown in Figure 6, in which the skin loads were reacted by four pins. The 3 and 6-ply specimens were loaded in the fixture shown in Figure 7, which partially supports the skin between parallel plates without clamping it. The difference in test fixtures was accounted for in the joint analysis that followed the testing.

Figure 6. Pull Test Fixture Used with 8-ply Specimens

Figure 7. Pull Test Fixture Used with 3 and 6-ply Specimens

There was some curvature to the skin because the specimens were cut from the same 60-inch diameter cylindrical structures as the test panels. The specimen rib was clamped between parallel steel plates with serrated faces. There was no indication of slippage between rib and clamp during the tests. A tensile load was applied to the rib, which induced bending in the skin. Large skin deflections occurred, as shown in Figure 8, until failure. Failure invariably consisted of separation of the rib from the skin. Failure surfaces presented in Figure 9 show a clean break between skin and rib with small resin ridges remaining on the skin where the radii resin pockets were.

Figure 8. Skin Bending During Pull Test

Figure 9. Rib and Skin Failure Surfaces

As can be seen in Figure 10, a micrograph of the rib/skin joint, the bond line between rib and skin is a layer of resin with resin pockets in the radii. These resin pockets are where the maximum skin bending moment occurs and where failure is believed to initiate.

Figure 10. Photomicrograph of Rib/Skin Joint

Test results show that specimen strength increases with skin thickness, as expected (Figure 11). The thicker the skin the less bending deflection and the lower the peel stress in the resin pocket at the radius. Individual specimen results are shown in Table 1. A finite element model of each type of specimen and fixture was created to determine critical strains in the resin at failure loads. Initial cracking was found from first drop in the measure load on each specimen.

Figure 11. Strength of Tee Specimens with 3-, 6-, and 8-ply Skin

Table 1. Test Results of 3-, 6-, and 8-ply Specimens

3-Ply Specimen	Initial crack (N/mm)	Failure (N/mm)	6-Ply Specimen	Initial crack (N/mm)	Failure (N/mm)	8-Ply Specimen	Initial Crack (N/mm)	Failure (N/mm)
3-1	4.637	8.170	6-1	11.39	16.29	8-1	22.89	23.7
3-2	3.312	6.295	6-2	11.33	11.33	8-2	20.90	24.7
3-3	4.442	5.329	6-3	8.170	8.82	8-3	18.39	18.7
3-4	4.078	6.646	6-4	14.01	14.01	8-4	20.55	25.5
3-5	1.808	3.221	6-5	12.38	12.38	8-5	16.41	16.4
3-6	3.311	3.799	6-6	10.33	10.33	8-6	15.19	19.22
Average	3.598	5.577	Average	11.27	12.19	8-7	17.5	25.28
Std Dev	1.04	1.851	Std Dev	1.96	2.67	Average	18.83	21.91
						Std Dev	2.68	3.71

ANALYSIS OF TEST PANELS

Three cylindrical grid-stiffened panels with 3-, 6-, and 8-ply skins were loaded in compression and tested until failure. Panel finite element models were constructed and analyzed with MSC.NASTRAN non-linear solution. Enforced displacements were applied on one of the transverse edges, while the other transverse edge had all degrees of freedom constrained. Knife-edge support on the longitudinal sides constrains the radial translation (Figure 12). The load applied to the panel model was increased gradually. The analysis results were correlated with tests and validated the failure criteria of the composite isogrid structures. The skin started to buckle early in the test. Multiple buckling waves were predicted for the 3-ply skin panel and observed during test (Figure 13). When the panel global buckling was reached, the stiffness matrix became singular and the analytical solution started to diverge. Shortly before global buckling, the model showed a drop in the axial load and a sharp increase in the radial displacements (Figure 14). These radial displacements are the peak values for the entire model at each load step.

Figure 12. Finite Element Model of Test Panel

Figure 13. Deformed Shape of 3-ply Skin FEM

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Figure 14. Predicted Loads and Displacements of 8-ply Skin Test Panel

Joint loads were extracted at nodes along the stiffeners and applied to the detailed joint model for the applied compression load corresponding to the test panel failure. The maximum strain invariant J1 in the panel fillet radius was compared with the allowable obtained from the T-specimen tests. An allowable J1 of 70% of the T-specimen average J1 would have predicted the joint failure for all 3 panels (Figure 15). The earlier failure of the 6-ply skin panel was attributed to a problem with the test fixture that caused a higher load to be applied on one side of the panel. However, the J1 allowable of 70% of the average T-specimen J1 resulted in conservative sizing of the Minotaur fairing.

Figure 15. First Strain Invariant at Test Panel Failure vs. T-Specimen Tests

CONCLUSIONS

The skin peel-off failure mode is specific to thin skin, grid-stiffened composite structures. The failure criteria and allowable strains were developed from small T-specimen tests, calibrated with panel tests and applied to the sizing of the Minotaur fairing. The skin peel-off failure is critical for thin skin panels where the skin is allowed to buckle. Understanding of the failure mechanism of the grid-stiffened composite structures opens the possibility for optimizing the panel geometry and improving the efficient of the design.

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